

Grant Agreement Number: 723265

Project acronym: **Clusters 2.0**

Project full title: Clusters 2.0 - Open network of hyper connected logistics clusters towards Physical Internet

D7.1

Communication strategy and plan

Due delivery date: 31/07/2017

Actual delivery date: 15/10/2017

Organization name of lead participant for this deliverable:

Project co-funded by the European Commission within Horizon 2020		
Dissemination level		
PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium	

Project funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme (2014 – 2020)

Document Control Sheet

Deliverable number:	D7.1
Deliverable responsible:	ENIDE
Work package:	WP7
Editor:	Francesc Rosinés

Author(s) – in alphabetical order		
Name	Organisation	E-mail
David Quesada	ENIDE	David.quesada@enide.com
J.Vicent Pastor	ENIDE	Jvicent.pastor@enide.com
Francesc Rosinés	ENIDE	Francesc.rosines@enide.com

Document Revision History			
Version	Date	Modifications Introduced	
0.0	1 Jun 2017	ToC	
0.1	30 Jun 2017	Initial version	
1.0 SFR	28 Jul 2017	Complete version, Submitted for review	
1.0	21 Ago 2017	Final, including comments from review process	

Legal Disclaimer

The information in this document is provided “as is”, and no guarantee or warranty is given that the information is fit for any particular purpose. The above referenced consortium members shall have no liability for damages of any kind including without limitation direct, special, indirect, or consequential damages that may result from the use of these materials subject to any liability which is mandatory due to applicable law. © 2017 by Clusters 2.0 Consortium.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Definition
EC	European Commission
PO	Project officer
GA	Grant Agreement
WP	Work Package

Table of Contents

1. Executive Summary	6
2. Introduction	6
2.1 Purpose of Document	6
2.2 Intended audience.....	7
3. General Communication and Dissemination Objectives	7
3.1 Background	7
3.2 Dissemination Objectives.....	7
4. Communication and Dissemination target groups.....	8
4.1 Logistics industry.....	8
4.2 ICT providers.....	8
4.3 Relevant EU, national and international initiatives.....	8
4.4 European and international organisations and technical communities.....	8
4.5 Scientific and research community	9
4.6 EC staff/politicians and relevant European Organizations.....	9
4.7 Key influencers / Publications	9
4.8 General public	9
5. Communication and Dissemination Plan	9
5.1 First phase activities.....	9
5.2 Second phase activities	10
5.3 Third phase activities	10
5.4 Activities after the project end.....	10
6. Communication and Dissemination toolbox	13
6.1 Establishing Clusters 2.0 as a brand	13
6.1.1 Project Logo	13
6.1.2 Project flyer and postcard	13
6.1.3 General presentation.....	14
6.1.4 Roll-up banner and posters.....	14
6.2 Media.....	15
6.2.1 Project video.....	15
6.2.2 Publication on demonstration actions and results.....	15
6.2.3 Press releases.....	16
6.2.4 Sectorial Newspapers/Journals publications	16
6.3 On-line tools	17
6.3.1 Web site	17
6.3.2 Newsletter	18
6.3.3 Social media.....	19
6.4 Project wrap-up and preparing for exploitation	19
6.5 Dissemination versus Communication channels	19
7. Dissemination toolbox.....	20
7.1 Dissemination procedure	20

Clusters 2.0

7.2	Open access	20
7.3	Results timeline of expected communicable results	21
7.4	Academic activities.....	22
7.5	Related initiatives	22
7.6	H2020 Dissemination Guidelines.....	28
7.6.1	Promoting the action — Visibility of EU funding: Communication activities by beneficiaries 28	
7.6.2	Dissemination of results — Open access — Visibility of EU funding.....	28
7.6.3	Open access to scientific publications	30
8.	Clusters 2.0 events and visibility at external events	23
8.1	Clusters 2.0 conferences	23
8.2	EHLIG meetings.....	23
8.3	External Advisory board meetings	23
8.4	External events.....	24
9.	Measuring the effectiveness of activities	25
9.1	Summary of Key performance indicators	25
9.2	Compliance with description of work.....	25
10.	Overview of resources	26
10.1	Overview of deliverables in WP 7	26
10.2	Overview of person-months per participant	26
10.3	Work plan	26
10.4	Overview of dissemination material direct costs.....	27
11.	Conclusion.....	27
12.	ANNEX I - Other Social media	28
12.1	Facebook.....	31
12.2	Wikipedia.....	31
12.3	Slideshare	32
12.4	Open access repository	32

1. Executive Summary

Logistics clusters become value creators for the regions where they are formed, where a mix of good intermodal connections, logistics platforms and large freight volumes are in place. Well-established logistics clusters still do not leverage their full potentials in terms of competitiveness and sustainability for the European industry and society, among other reasons, due to:

- Not enough coordination between the local actors in the cluster,
- Not enough connectivity and coordination between European logistics clusters to maximize the full network potential of the clusters and related hubs.

Moreover, logistics clusters also need to deal and minimize negative impacts such as congestion, noise, land use and local pollution.

Following the main project objective that is to enhance the competitiveness and sustainability of the Clusters, a lot of efforts is needed to make them aware of new possibilities and concepts, including enabling them to take part of Clusters networks and corridors' flows. These efforts include a variety of dissemination actions leading to understanding benefits resulting from the innovative solutions being developed.

This deliverable includes the communication, dissemination and liaison strategy and plan to be followed within the project. The dissemination strategy defines the goals for the dissemination activities of the project. These are being achieved by reaching the specified communication and dissemination target groups through defined dissemination channels.

2. Introduction

2.1 Purpose of Document

The Clusters 2.0 Project activities have set ambitious targets in terms of opening the way for leverage the full potentials of logistics clusters in terms of competitiveness and sustainability. A concise dissemination strategy, therefore, is of major importance for the maximization of the project's impact to the scientific community, the industry, the society and for the successful deployment of its results. The consortium's intention is to widely disseminate the existence of the project goals and results not only within Europe but also internationally, in order to highlight Europe as a major force worldwide in the relevant scientific and industrial field. In this document the communication and dissemination strategy and plans designed for this purpose are presented.

The dissemination strategy defines the goals for the dissemination activities of the project. These are being achieved by reaching the specified dissemination target groups through defined dissemination channels. The ways to reach the target groups depends on the stage of the work progress of the project. While at the early stages of the project the dissemination is concentrated on presentations of the idea and concept of the work to be deployed, at later stages the dissemination task will focus on presenting the achieved developments and results. All these are described in the dissemination roadmap which provides a draft outline of the dissemination activities and their presented content per year of the project.

Dissemination activities are important for the Consortium also on a partner level. Making the Consortium partners' competencies known can prove beneficial for promoting their activities

as well. It is expected that regardless the partnership in the specific project WP, all partners will take part in Communication and Dissemination activities even at a different level. This contribution can take several forms, from artistic design in the dissemination material to scientific review of papers in workshops, conference participation, exhibitions etc. Thus, it is essential that all partners have an overall idea of their planned dissemination activities either for Clusters 2.0 purposes exclusively or for general purposes where Clusters 2.0 will also be represented. The dissemination activities are managed by the Dissemination Leader and specific dissemination procedures are followed which are also described within the document.

2.2 Intended audience

This document is addressed to the Consortium members.

3. General Communication and Dissemination Objectives

3.1 Background

The overall aim of the Clusters 2.0 communication and dissemination framework is to promote the project, its mission and results to a wide range of stakeholders at European, national, regional, local and international levels. It is important to communicate with a far-reaching audience and each level of governance has different stakeholders which Clusters 2.0 needs to address. Therefore, the project will adopt a cross-level dissemination approach.

The project also aims to establish the project and its tools as a reference point for the logistics industry and the logistics clusters in particular. This aspect is increasingly important for the legacy of the project and aims to encourage the actual take-up and deployment of the Clusters 2.0 solution after the project has finished.

A key objective of Clusters 2.0 is to develop effective communication interfaces and dissemination channels. All of the dissemination tools will have a clear message and explain the objectives and mission of the project in a consistent and coherent way. All of the separate communication tools (described later) will aim to attract the interest of all of the target groups and will be designed to match the common project identity.

The project will also communicate the role of the EU and the H2020 Programme through all of the communication and dissemination channels. It is important to promote the programme supporting Clusters 2.0 and showcase similar successful projects to boost the overall success of the project.

3.2 Dissemination Objectives

The overall aim of Clusters 2.0 dissemination framework is to promote the project, its mission and results to a wide group of stakeholders, described in Section 4, and achieve the largest possible impact, in order to build consensus and to raise awareness around the achievements of innovations and best practices developed in the project, and to exploit the results to benefit the implementation of the Clusters 2.0 key innovations

Through different targeted activities and dedicated communication tools, the Clusters 2.0 Dissemination Strategy:

Clusters 2.0

- Defining a dissemination framework, with dedicated dissemination tools and channels which are adapted to respective target groups
- Organising and facilitating events with input from all WPs
- Establishing synergy in dissemination with relevant other initiatives
- Presenting Clusters 2.0 at internal and external events

4. Communication and Dissemination target groups

4.1 Logistics industry

This group includes the following sub-groups:

- Large LSPs, Freight integrators
- Shippers/Cargo owners
- Logistics' SMEs
- Clusters' responsible and managers
- Transport network managers and infrastructure operators (Roads, Ports, inland waters, etc.)

This group comprises both business and technical experts. The communication direction can be both external to the consortium and internal towards the project partners.

4.2 ICT providers

This group covers developers of logistics-related applications and ICT service providers, to discuss the product emergence and their commercial expectations. Positive feedback is expected to enhance the commercial attractiveness of ICT products and services.

4.3 Relevant EU, national and international initiatives

Dissemination within the research community is one of the pre-requisites for successful project implementation. Knowledge exchange is crucial for assessing the state-of-the-art, project planning and evaluating project results.

This target group will be addressed via different ways: individually, within the framework of international organisations in which researchers maintain international exchange and cooperation, and by official contact at project level.

This effort will have an international scope. European, but also overseas high profile colleagues involved in similar research activities will be addressed.

4.4 European and international organisations and technical communities

This is a wide group of individual associations (i.e. relevant EC/national projects, ETP's such as ALICE, ERRAC, ERTRAC or Waterborne), at European, national and international level, which have significant multiplier potential as associations representing transport authorities and members of the Logistics industry.

4.5 Scientific and research community

The results of the project will be broadly disseminated to the scientific community through participation in the most important academic conferences and logistics related events.

4.6 EC staff/politicians and relevant European Organizations

This group includes EC staff/politicians, relevant European Organizations (ESC, GS1, ECTRI etc.), policy advisors and key opinion creators.

This will facilitate a clearer overall understanding of the topic and consequently will provide an evident support for decision making activities at higher level.

This group includes standarization fora and initiatives where the results and project recommendations will be communicate.

4.7 Key influencers / Publications

EU wide, national, regional, online and specialist publications

4.8 General public

Informing and communicating with the public as well as fostering societal debate have already become integral constituents of the portfolio of European initiatives. For this audience, key-messages should focus on the overall concept rather than on specific technical solutions.

5. Communication and Dissemination Plan

The selection of the appropriate dissemination channel and the respective message to be disseminated heavily depends on the stage that the project is at each specific moment. At the early phases of the project, the focus is on transmitting the project concept and the idea of the research work. Towards the end of the project, however, more technical presentations and publications can be realised as new findings will be available. Having this in mind, the Communication and Dissemination plan has been determined and is presented below. This Plan provides the outline of how the dissemination channels and materials will be used for reaching each of the specified target group per year of the project.

5.1 First phase activities

During the first part of the project, the dissemination activities are aiming to generally inform the public, relevant research, academic and logistics community and all relevant stakeholders on the Clusters 2.0 objectives and expected results. These activities are setting

the basis for the whole communication and dissemination policy since most of the communication and dissemination material will be produced at this stage and will be used for the duration of the project. The informative leaflets and roll-up have being designed and are going to be disseminated to various events. In addition, the website has already been developed including information about the project and it will be updated. The publications and presentations of this period will be describing mainly the project concept and research methodology. At this stage, the main activities are related to Communication, rather than Dissemination.

This phase covers from project start to first findings obtained, approximately in M14

5.2 Second phase activities

During the second part of the project some results will already be available. Thus, the aim of the communication and dissemination activities within this period will be to publish the first findings and describe the future work to be performed. The research community, logistics industry and policy-making authorities and decision-making stakeholders, end users etc., will form the target groups of the publications and project presentations to be performed during this phase. Technical papers will be submitted to scientific conferences as well as to workshops and events. The communication and dissemination material will be the same as developed in the first phase while the website will be continuously updated with newer project achievements.

This phase covers from first findings to completion of the set of tools, approximately in M28.

5.3 Third phase activities

During the final part of the project there will be a major effort of disseminating the project results to all target groups using every dissemination channel available. Press releases and mass media will be employed for transmitting the Clusters 2.0 message. Technical papers presenting the final results will be published to journals and to various international and European industry and scientific conferences, while demonstrations of solutions and prototypes will be given at relevant exhibitions. At this phase several papers submissions to scientific journals are expected. The website will continuously be updated with the latest developments and information and the final project deliverables will be available for downloading.

This phase covers from the completion of tools to the end of the project, including the execution on the living labs. It is important to mention that depending of the individual living lab and their related tools, a time of coexistence between different phases will occur.

5.4 Activities after the project end

Even after the project termination there is still a high possibility to support and promote the project impact to the wider community. All final results will be available for consultation and exploitation and this will be facilitated by appropriate dissemination activities. The Clusters 2.0 website will be sustained after the end of the project for at least five years in order to provide all interested stakeholders with information on project achievements and findings and details on contact persons for more information.

5.1 Results time table

The below table shows the planned timeline for results availability, as well as the expected communicable results and the audience addressed (described in ch.4):

Id	Time	Date	Expected results	Audience addressed
R1	M6	Oct 2017	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Scoping logistics clusters. - Preliminary exploitation plans. - Consolidated LL requirements. - CNI Technical description - Collaboration and negotiation mechanisms 1st description 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Logistics Industry -ICT providers -Relevant initiatives
R2	M12	Apr 2018	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Technical specifications on LL prototypes - Exploitation handbook - Market analysis 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Logistics Industry -ICT providers -Relevant initiatives
R3	M16	Aug 2018	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CluCS architecture and 1st prototype - 1st Prototype on cross cluster collaboration - 1st Prototype on NMLU 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Logistics Industry -ICT providers -Relevant initiatives -EC&EU authorities
R4	M20	Dec 2018	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - LL feedback on 1st prototypes - Recommendations on policies and technical standards (M18) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Logistics Industry -ICT providers -Relevant initiatives -EU tech organizations -EC&EU authorities -Influencers & publications
R5	M24-26	Apr-Jun 2019	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Exploitation plans update - 2nd iteration on prototypes, architecture and methodology 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Logistics Industry -ICT providers -Relevant initiatives -EU tech organizations -EC&EU authorities -Influencers & publications
R6	M30-32	Nov 2019-Jan 2020	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Guidelines for Smart Cluster establishment path - 3rd iteration on prototypes, architecture and methodology - LL validation and conclusions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Logistics Industry -ICT providers -Relevant initiatives -EU tech organizations -EC&EU authorities -Influencers & publications
R7	M36	Apr 2020	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Final exploitation plans - Consolidated LL results (M34) - Impact assessment - Recommendations on policies and technical standards 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Logistics Industry -ICT providers -Relevant initiatives -EU tech organizations -EC&EU authorities

Id	Time	Date	Expected results	Audience addressed
				-Influencers & publications

6. Communication and Dissemination toolbox

The communication and dissemination toolbox is divided in several sections:

- Establishing Clusters 2.0 as a brand
- Mass media
- On-line tools

Below, these sections are developed. The related initial material described in these sections are presented in the document *Clusters 2.0 D7.2 Dissemination material*.

6.1 Establishing Clusters 2.0 as a brand

The below table summarise the subjects (further described later) with the related results and the expected audience:

Subject	Related Results	Audience						
		Logistics industry	ICT Providers	EU & Nat org and Tech c.	Scientific & R+I com.	EC and EU authorities	Influencers & publications	General public
Project logo	General communication	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Project flyer	General communication	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
General presentation	General communication	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Roll-up and posters	General communication	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

6.1.1 Project Logo

Description

A logo (abbreviation of logotype) is a graphic mark, emblem, or symbol commonly used to aid and promote instant public recognition.

Use:

The project flyer logo has been produced electronically in high-definition PNG format

6.1.2 Project flyer and postcard

Description

Project flyer is a brief presentation of the project concept, challenges and characteristics of developed solutions. It should be presented with the use of graphics, pictures, icons and graphs reflecting the project idea.

Use:

The project flyer has been produced electronically in PDF format and made available on the project website. An English version will be printed. The printed version will be distributed during different events, including internal project events such as workshops and meetings with stakeholders as well as external events such as conferences, fairs and exhibitions, seminars and other meetings with logistics industry. The electronic version will be produced in different languages of the project partners in order to reach the widest possible target audience in a number of countries. Since the flyer is to have a lifespan that will encompass the whole duration of the project it will be written in an open style, such that it is fresh and appealing for catching the audience.

Moreover, project postcard has been prepared and will be printed to be made available at meetings with logistics industry.

We estimate to distribute 1.000 flyers and postcards in the events where Clusters 2.0 and its consortium participates.

6.1.3 General presentation

Description

The general project presentation is an electronic presentation comprising of few slides introducing the main project idea. The text is in most cases presented in bullet points accompanied by pictures, icons, links to websites, etc.

Use:

The general project presentation will be used during different events, including internal project events such as project works hops, meetings with stakeholders and external events such as conferences, fairs and exhibitions, seminars and other meetings with logistics industry players. The presentation is made in English and should be translated into other partners languages if needed for the communication with the stakeholders in partner countries.

6.1.4 Roll-up banner and posters

Description

The project roll-ups and posters is a large one page graphical presentation or picture of the project idea. The design of project roll-ups and posters is of high relevance and therefore it must follow the “corporate identity” pattern (logo, images, colours, fonts). Its purpose is to capture attention and advertise the project. Its basic content should include:

- Acronym and name of the project
- Logos and slogan of the project

Use

During the project, roll-ups and posters will be designed for specific events or purposes. They will be used to provide an eye-catching and thought-provoking presentation, and to include contact or website details giving ready access to further information. It will be printed and used at exhibitions, conferences and public meetings.

6.2 Media

The below table summarise the subjects (further described later) with the related results and the expected audience:

Subject	Related Results	Audience						
		Logistics industry	ICT Providers	EU & Nat org and Tech c.	Scientific & R+I com.	EC and EU authorities	Influencers & publications	General public
Project video	General communication	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Publication on demonstrations	R3, R5, R6	X	X	X			X	
Press releases	R3, R5, R6	X		X		X	X	X
Generalist Journals publications	R3, R5, R6, R7					X		X
Specialised Journals publications	R3, R5, R6, R7	X	X	X	X		X	

6.2.1 Project video

Description

The project video is an interactive presentation in the form of a movie briefly introducing the project idea, its results and characteristics of developed solutions using simple messages.

Use

It will be presented in English and made available through the project web site and other available channels, platforms such as YouTube, forums supporting the project realisation and in social media.

We estimate 3 project videos during project life, being the most complete the last one, presenting the results of the project.

6.2.2 Publication on demonstration actions and results

Description

The form of a booklet is planned to be used for the publication of the project demonstration actions and results.

Use

In this document the Clusters 2.0 concept will be explained, as well as the living labs cases and the results obtained from its execution. Document will be distributed in electronic format among project subscribers and partners networks, but printed copies will be produced on demand.

6.2.3 Press releases

Description

Press releases are intended to communicate the project's progress or announce important achievements. Press release is usually a one page note presenting the message briefly, using simple language.

Use

All project members are expected to contribute to the dissemination of project results through appropriate press releases in their respective countries throughout the duration of the project. Especially Living Labs leaders are requested to produce press releases on the results achieved. When such a press release is published, an electronic copy must be sent to the dissemination leader, in order to be uploaded on the project web site. In addition, some details should be given by the partner in charge: source, publication date, target audience.

A press release example has been included as part of *D7.2 Dissemination material*.

6.2.4 Sectorial Newspapers/Journals publications

Description

Publication of the project in Newspapers and Journals in the form of articles (not advertisement).

Use

The project partners will be asked to analyse the possibility to present the project in sectorial Newspapers/Journals according the cost/benefit principle.

List of potential business and scientific journals (to be expanded during the project):

Business and Scientific Journals	Comment
Journal of Logistics Management	
Logistics Research	Open access journal
The International Journal of Logistics Management	
International Journal of Logistics Systems and Management	
Journal of Supply Chain Management Science	Open access journal
International Journal of Information Systems and Supply Chain Management	
ACM Transactions on Internet Technology	Technical journal – has a Special Section on Internet of Things (IoT)
International Journal of Physical Distribution and Logistics Management	Provides business practitioners, consultants and academics with leading edge information and discussions of current developments in the field
Logistics Manager	Monthly magazine for managers in charge of the supply chain of UK industrial, retail and commercial organisations.
International Journal of Managing Value and Supply Chains (IJMVSC)	Quarterly open access peer-reviewed journal that publishes articles that contribute new results in all areas of value and supply chain management.
International Journal of Logistics: Research and Applications	A leading journal of supply chain management which publishes original and challenging work that has a clear

	applicability to the business world.
International Journal of Operations & Production Management (IJOPM)	Investigates opportunities and problems of developing and implementing strategies, systems, and practice in operations management.

Clusters 2.0 plans to publish at least 5 scientific papers in international journals or conferences.

6.3 On-line tools

In this section, several on-line tools are reviewed. Then, an analysis of the potential use of them to the objectives related to the Clusters 2.0 internet community presence is done; the final goal is to select the most suitable ones, defining the potential use of them.

The below table summarise the subjects (further described later) with the related results and the expected audience:

Subject	Related Results	Audience						
		Logistics industry	ICT Providers	EU & Nat org and Tech c.	Scientific & R+I com.	EC and EU authorities	Influencers & publications	General public
Web site	General communication	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Newsletter	R3, R5, R6	X	X	X			X	
Social media	R3, R5, R6	X		X		X	X	X

6.3.1 Web site

Description

As stated in the Clusters 2.0 Description of Work, the project web site is a major channel for visibility of the Clusters 2.0 project: it describes the project and its aims and highlights living labs goals and results to be achieved. The project web site also serves as an interactive tool for internal and external communication. It provides a place to share public documents, updates on the current research phases and results, presents further developments and advice about upcoming events.

Use

As said before, the website will be the key stone for the building of the internet community for Clusters 2.0. It will centralize the content provided from the project among the other web 2.0 tools, trying to organize a common approach among all them and taking profit of the different features of the others.

Recognizing that the project website/portal is an important resource in disseminating information about the project, facilitating collaboration amongst partners, and bringing together a diverse and scattered community of interest around the project's activities, we have foreseen the following activities to improve its usability and features, and to market it for increased traffic and searchability. The goal is to make the portal a true source of

information and contact point for further collaboration.

The following actions have been foreseen:

- Improving and updating content to be relevant and rich in keywords density;
- Introducing Search Engine Marketing parameters such as keyword density, quality titles, headers and images, etc.;
- Improving visitor satisfaction by improving site layout, design and navigation, reducing complexity, improving search facilities, dedicated host, etc.

We have the goal of 5.000 unique page views, enabled by the mentioned actions as well as SEO techniques

Community Manager

In order to execute this strategy and to mobilize the different efforts to provide contents and materials for all these tools, it is necessary to define a single responsible for these activities. This role will need:

- To be aware about the technical and scientific activities and findings of the project;
- To be aware of the different dissemination actions of the project;
- To channelize the feedback received from the audience;
- To coordinate the consortium partners to enhance the impact of the dissemination of the tools;
- To gather all this information to provide contents and materials for the Web tools, especially creating an open discussion around the concepts of the project.

Dissemination manager will act initially as Community Manager of Clusters 2.0.

6.3.2 Newsletter

Description

A newsletter is a regularly distributed publication generally about one main topic that is of interest to its subscribers. Newspapers and leaflets are types of newsletters. Additionally, newsletters delivered electronically via email (e-Newsletters) have gained rapid acceptance for the same reasons as email in general has gained popularity over printed correspondence. Newsletters have become common source of informing specific audience on issues of their interest. For example, newsletters are given out at schools, to inform parents about things that happen in that school.

Sending newsletters to customers and prospects is a common marketing strategy, which can have benefits and drawbacks. General attributes of newsletters include news and upcoming events of the related organization, as well as contact information for general inquiries.

Use

The project newsletter will be also a very important tool for the communication of the project goals. Concerning the use for the internet community building, a double method will be used: 1) the existing versions will be available at the web site; 2) it will be actively distributed in two different ways, with a mailing list for an interest group and also through the project consortium partners and EHLIG.

The Clusters 2.0 newsletters will be oriented to offer information to project stakeholders, focusing on aims and results instead of in project internal organization or activities. In each newsletter we plan to include an interview with a key project member (only one per newsletter, e.g. coordinator, individual living lab responsables) as well as the most important highlights (in terms of results) during the period covered.

A total of five e-newsletters will be produced, one every six months during the project to keep the Clusters 2.0 community informed about the project's progress and results. Short and snappy articles on the project's activities and demonstrations will give a good impression to the different target groups Clusters 2.0 intends to reach. The newsletter will also provide an opportunity to expand the project's database via the subscription option on the Clusters 2.0 website.

Number	Due date
E-newsletter 1	October 2017
E-newsletter 2	April 2018
E-newsletter 3	October 2018
E-newsletter 4	April 2019
E-newsletter 5	October 2019

The related KPI include the newsletter distributed to 150 signed persons at M12 and 300 persons at project end, achieved through a mix of actions in the website and other social media.

6.3.3 Social media

Next to classic electronic channels like email and a web portal, Social Media will need consideration. Because of the ease of communication and the groups involved, the dynamics of communication be intense and messages can get warped if conversations are left alone, once Clusters 2.0 news has been picked up by certain Social Media. Social Media will be applied in specific situations like indicated hereafter:

- Twitter: In case to be applied at specific conferences and workshops, using a hashtag assigned by the conference/workshop organizer. The '#CLUSTERS20_EU' combined with a hashtag of the conference/workshop will be used for specific workshops.
- LinkedIn: will be used to create interest groups with discussion and to post blogs and newsfeeds.

Other social media such as YouTube, SlideShare or Wikipedia are considered in Annex I section.

We expect 1000 twitter followers reached by cross following actions, and 250 LinkedIn group members, achieved through an activity and collaboration of the Consortium members professional accounts, as well as communication of the addresses using posters, flyers, web site, etc. In addition, we expect to have social media links with at less 10 representative groups from across the EU.

6.4 Project wrap-up and preparing for exploitation

This final phase of the project will present the results and overall results of the project. The final event will be the main opportunity to showcase the Clusters 2.0 results and how clusters can benefit from using these results. This event will also be the start of the post-project CLUSTER 2.0 take-up.

6.5 Dissemination versus Communication channels

Channels	Communication	Dissemination
Project website – General presentation pages	X	

Project website – Specific pages dedicated to outputs		X
Mailing lists & Contact databases – General	X	X
Social media	X	
External channels – Generalist	X	
External channels – Specialised, sectorial, targeted		X
Project events – Presentation of project outputs		X
External events – Announcements, brochures and flyers, etc	X	
External events – Presentation of project results		X
Publications in scientific magazines		X

7. Dissemination toolbox

In addition to the below description of the dissemination toolbox, Dissemination actions has to follow the Horizon 2020 rules, described in Annex I – H2020 guidelines.

7.1 Dissemination procedure

Dissemination activities conditions are **fixed in Clusters 2.0 Consortium Agreement**.

Among other obligations and conditions agreed, the following excerpts has to be highlighted:

- During the Project and for a period of 1 year after the end of the Project, the dissemination of own Results by one or several Parties including but not restricted to publications and presentations, shall be governed by the procedure of Article 29.1 of the Grant Agreement subject to the following provisions.

Prior notice of any planned publication shall be given to the other Parties at least 45 calendar days before the publication. Any objection to the planned publication shall be made in accordance with the Grant Agreement in writing to the Coordinator and to the Party or Parties proposing the dissemination within 30 calendar days after receipt of the notice. If no objection is made within the time limit stated above, the publication is permitted.

- A Party shall not include in any dissemination activity another Party's Results or Background without obtaining the owning Party's prior written approval, unless they are already published.
- The Parties undertake to cooperate to allow the timely submission, examination, publication and defence of any dissertation or thesis for a degree which includes their Results or Background subject to the confidentiality and publication provisions agreed in this Consortium Agreement.

7.2 Open access

Article 29.2 states that it is **MANDATORY** that each beneficiary **MUST** ensure **open access** (free of charge, online access for any user) to ALL peer reviewed scientific publication relating its results

- Green model. After an embargo period benefiting the publisher, the scientific author/s publishes in an open repository the article/paper
- Gold model. The scientific author allow (i.e. by payment) to the publisher to allow immediate open access to readers

Clusters 2.0 will use an Open Repository to store and provide access to publications and researchers profiles.

Scientific information refers to peer-reviewed scientific research articles (published in scholarly journals), pre-print articles, conference papers, patents, books and research data (data underlying publications, curated data and/or raw data).

7.3 Timeline of expected communicable results

Dissemination are supported by publications, i.e., deliverables considered as public and communications to academic and technical publications and events.

Regarding the deliverables considered as “Public” the below table list it, including the ID of the results that links with the above table:

Deliv. Nr	Deliverable name	Delivery date (M)	Related Results Id	Logistics industry	ICT Providers	EU & Nat org and Tech c.	Scientific & R+I com.	EC and EU authorities	Influencers & publications
D2.1	Scoping Logistics Clusters	6	R1	X					X
D2.2	Cluster building blocks: Proximity Terminal Network potentialities	6	R1	X	X				
D3.1	CNI Description of the minimal data set	6	R1		X		X		
D3.2	CNI API description	6	R1		X		X		
D4.1	Specification sheet of designated NMLU	6	R1	X		X			X
D4.4	Reliable train-truck horizontal transshipment prototype	6	R1	X		X			X
D1.1	Market Analysis	12	R2	X	X				X
D1.4	Exploitation Handbook	12	R2	X	X				X
D4.2	Reliable NMLU prototype	14	R3	X		X	X		X
D2.3	Cluster Community System requirements and architecture	16	R3		X	X	X		
D2.4	Cluster Community System Tool	16	R3	X	X	X	X		
D2.5	Handbook for Smart Clusters development	16	R3	X	X	X	X	X	X
D3.3	Collaboration methodology within logistics clusters	16	R3	X		X	X	X	
D3.5	Rail Freight Operators Service mapping	16	R3	X		X		X	
D3.6	Network Design Model describing current European flows across clusters: as is	16	R3	X		X		X	X
D7.5	Policy adaptation and standardization recommendations	18	R4	X	X	X	X	X	X
D4.3	Prototype trucks for fast and reliable transshipment of NMLUs	22	R4	X		X	X		X
D3.4	Collaboration methodology in between logistics clusters	26	R4	X		X	X		X
D3.8	Scenarios and tools for shipment planning and asset optimisation for logistics clusters networks	28	R5	X		X	X		X
D4.5	Dynamic Terminal Management System	28	R5		X		X		
D3.7	Optimization and assessment tool for sustainable collaboration through clusters: to be	30	R6		X		X		

Deliv. Nr	Deliverable name	Delivery date (M)	Related Results Id	Logistics industry	ICT Providers	EU & Nat org and Tech c.	Scientific & R+I com.	EC and EU authorities	Influencers & publications
D5.8	High-level reports on progress of Living Labs	34	R7	X		X	X		
D6.3	Living Lab evaluation analysis and Clusters Assessment Report	36	R7			X	X		X
D6.4	Environmental and socio-economic performance assessment of Clusters 2.0	36	R7	X		X	X	X	X

In addition, the project plans to publish 5 scientific papers in international journals or conferences. The below table shows a tentative list of schedule and contents related to these scientific papers

Paper Id	Issuing date	Related Results Id	Logistics industry	ICT Providers	EU & Nat org and Tech c.	Scientific & R+I com.	EC and EU authorities	Influencers & publications
P1	M12	R1, R2	X	X		X		
P2	M16	R3	X	X		X		
P3	M20	R4	X	X		X		X
P4	M26	R5	X			X		X
P5	M36	R6, R7	X	X	X	X	X	

7.4 Academic activities

As part of the project the following activities will be started:

- M.Sc. theses
- Ph.D. projects

A tentative initial goal of 5 M.Sc. theses and 2 Ph.D. projects has been fixed.

7.5 Related initiatives

Several initiatives, both ongoing and future will be contacted in order to work on cross-fertilization, align expectative and avoid duplicities. Among them:

Clusters 2.0

- AEOLIX
- ATROPINE
- SELIS
- SmartBOX
- Kombi-Flex Waggon

We expect to have at least 10 EU or national projects and initiatives

8. Clusters 2.0 events and visibility at external events

The Clusters 2.0 events will come as a dissemination support to project objectives. They will help in spreading the project outputs to the respective target audiences, facilitate valuable feedback from respective stakeholders, and provide ground for discussion and brainstorming.

8.1 Clusters 2.0 conferences

Two conferences will be organised by Clusters 2.0 to underpin the communication and dissemination of the project. Partners will undertake the participation of Clusters 2.0 to events, where the content of dissemination material will be adapted to the target audience.

A **Clusters 2.0 Mid-term Conference** will be organised approximately in M18. This event will aim at presenting ongoing progress and results of the project, debate and endorse the Clusters 2.0 Blueprints and Solutions, as well as promoting the Clusters 2.0 approach to targeted audiences.

A **Clusters 2.0 Final Conference** is planned to take place at the end of the project. During the event the final project results will be presented.

8.2 EHLIG meetings

The EHLIG (European High Level Industrial Group) consists of 25 members, which are experts in logistics both from academia and industry. EHLIG Members will meet twice a year, and will be fully reimbursed for travel and accommodation expenses incurred for the attendance of the EHLIG Meetings and other activities of the project they attend. The EHLIG will provide expert advice and feedback on selected CLUSTERS 2.0 results. The EHLIG will also be consulted when the strategy for effective communication is defined. EHLIG meetings will be planned in conjunction with workshops or conferences of the project, where key representatives from stakeholder groups will also be invited to participate. The goal will be to present the main results of the project as well as to seek stakeholder commitment beyond the life of the project involving them in results exploitation.

The EHLIG will have the following objectives: 1) Discuss the project major findings and seek endorsement 2) Evaluate whether the results match real needs 3) Provide direction to resources and access to end users 4) Help communicate project findings and activities 5) Assess emerging trends, opportunities, innovations and developing needs that may affect project concepts. 6) Assess whether to adapt project activities so that needs are met.

8.3 External Advisory board meetings

An External Advisory Board (EAB) will be appointed and steered by the Project Management

Team. The EAB will be chaired by the Coordinator. The role of the EAB will be to advise and consult the project on the approach, methodology and activities adopted. Tentative initial members are:

- Paul Ham. ECT Rotterdam
- Martin van der Meer. Head of Transport Management SC Europe TATA Steel
- Nik Delmeire. Secretary General European Shippers Council
- Wim Baert. Director Logistics Samsonite Europe NV

Formally, the members of the board are not part of the consortium and as such will be a consultative body for the project boards. The project will use advises to improve the deliverables and their acceptance. The members of the board will however not be entitled to steer the project processes or activities.

The goal is to have representatives of at least 15 EU and associated countries.

8.4 External events

Clusters 2.0 will arrange for its participation and representation in a number of European and International events, such as workshops, congresses and conferences, and this will continue throughout its duration. In this way the project partners can interact with people belonging to the scientific community, industry representatives and public administration officers as well as with the general public. Within these events Clusters 2.0 will present its work via technical presentations, organisation of special sessions on related research or exhibition of the project's concepts and findings at stands and booths. Also, FABRIC dissemination material such as brochures and posters will be distributed to the events participants so that a greater audience may be reached. Although the project is still at its start, Clusters 2.0 has already organized a session in 4th IPIC conference organized in Graz in July 2017 and in Munich Logistics Fair.

The following table lists relevant potential events for the coming years.

Event	Date	Place
TRA Transport Research Arena	16 Apr 2018	Vienna
Transport logistic Fair Munich	May (annual)	Munich
International Transport Forum (ITF)		
Transportation Research Board Annual Meeting		
IOT Solutions World Congress		
Mobile World Congress	February (annual)	Barcelona
World Conference cities and ports		
IPIC International Physical Internet Conference	Jul 2018	NL
SIL Barcelona	Jun (annual)	Barcelona
ILS (Information Systems, Logistics and Supply Chain) Conference 2016		
International Transport Forum (ITF)		
Intertraffic		
Salon International du transport et de la logistique du grand sud atlantique		
Future Highways		
European Week of Regions and Cities		
EyeForTransport		

ECTRI		
GS1 Global Forum		
EXPO logistics,		
European Freight and Logistics Leaders Forum		
Conferences of ALICE (ETP for Logistics),		
Supply Chain Summit		
IEEE Intelligent Transportation Systems Conference		

As part of the project, the consortium will be present at least in 5 scientific workshops.

9. Measuring the effectiveness of activities

9.1 Summary of Key performance indicators

- A website that generates over **5.000** unique page views;
- At least **150** individuals/organisations signed up to receive email updates on project achievements and results by M12 and at least **300** by project end;
- Media coverage that is equivalent to **150,000€** of advertising spend (an accepted industry measure);
- At least **5** peer-reviewed scientific publications in international journals or conferences;
- Participation in at least **5** scientific workshops;
- Presentation of project results in at least **10** international events and active distribution of at least **1,000** leaflets at such international events;
- Networked with at least **10** EU or national projects or initiatives;
- An External Advisory Board with members from at least **15** different EU countries;
- At least **5** M.Sc. theses and **2** Ph.D. projects;
- Over **1,000** twitter followers for the project;
- Over **250** members on LinkedIn Group;
- At least **3** project Videos uploaded to YouTube generating over **500** views in total;
- Social media links with at least **10** representative groups from across the EU.

9.2 Compliance with description of work

In order to ensure we fulfill our contractual obligations the number of publications; number of events and viewing figures for newsletters and website will be recorded by stakeholder group if possible. This metric is necessary but not sufficient to monitor the effectiveness of dissemination.

10. Overview of resources

10.1 Overview of deliverables in WP 7

The following deliverables are planned in WP7:

#	Title	Responsible	Type	Diss. level	Due date	Date
D7.1	Communication Strategy and Plan	ENIDE	Report	Public	M3	July 2017
D7.2	Communication kit	ENIDE	Web sites, etc	Public	M3	July 2017
D7.3	Engagement activities plan	ARGUSI	Report	Confidential	M6	Oct 2017
D7.4	Engagement activities Report	ARGUSI	Report	Confidential	M18	Oct 2018
D7.5	Policy adaptation and standardization recommendations	PTV	Report	Public	M18	Oct 2018
D7.6	Dissemination report	ENIDE	Report	Public	M36	Apr 2020

10.2 Overview of person-months per participant

	PTV	ENIDE	MOS	PGBS	IBI	IML	EURALOG	SEABILITY	NALLIAN	VAN ECK	ARMINES	PCT	ARGUSI	UIC	TOTAL
WP7 Communication	4,0	8,0	1,5	1,0	1,0	1,0	1,5	1,5	1,5	1,5	2,0	1,5	4,5	2,5	33,0
T7.1 Definition of Communication Strategy and Plan	0,5	1,5													2,0
T7.2.Clusters 2.0 Communication Tools and activities		3,0													3,0
T7.3 Use of foreground and Dissemination	1,5	3,0	0,5	0,5	1,0			1,0	0,5	1,0	1,0	0,5	1,0		11,5
T7.4 Clusters 2.0 Engagement Activities	1,0	0,5	1,0	0,5		0,5	1,5	0,5	1,0	0,5	1,0	1,0	3,5	1,5	14,0
T7.5 Policy adaptation and standardization activities	1,0					0,5								1,0	2,5

10.3 Work plan

10.4 Overview of dissemination material direct costs

Partner	Item Type	Item	Cost	Rationale
ENIDE	Material	Dissemination material	9.500	Video + other printed material
IBI	Material	Dissemination material	3.000	Project leaflet + other dissemination material
EURALOGISTIC	Material	Dissemination material	3.000	Project leaflet + other dissemination material
PCT		Dissemination material	3.000	Project leaflet + other dissemination material
ARGUSI		Dissemination material	3.000 (10.000)	Project leaflet + other dissemination material
PTV	Material	Dissemination material	3.000	Project leaflet + other dissemination material
ARGUSI	Travels	Travels of EHLIG	45.000	Travels and subsistence (750e each) of EHLIG executives to participate in 6 physical meetings over the project
ARGUSI	Material	Event costs	25.000	Clusters 2.0 workshops

11. Conclusion

Communication and Dissemination activities are of major importance for the Clusters 2.0 project and therefore a significant number of communication and dissemination activities are planned for its duration. To coordinate the activities there is a need for a concise strategy. In this deliverable, the strategy and plan designed especially for the Clusters 2.0 project is presented. The goals of the dissemination activity have been set, the dissemination materials to be used have been designed and the dissemination channels to reach the specified target groups have been also defined. All these dissemination elements are combined in a concise roadmap that is supervised by the Dissemination Leader according to specific procedures. A major focus is put on the project website which is designed to be as user friendly and attractive as possible. Finally, the deliverable presents the basic procedures for the organisation, control and execution of all project dissemination activities

12. ANNEX I – H2020 guidelines

12.1 H2020 Dissemination Guidelines

For Horizon 2020 projects the reference document for communication, dissemination and exploitation activities is the Grant Agreement (GA), and namely Articles 29 (Dissemination of results — Open access — Visibility of EU funding) and 38 (Promoting the action — Visibility of EU funding).

12.1.1 Promoting the action — Visibility of EU funding: Communication activities by beneficiaries

Regarding article 38, these are the rules to follow:

Obligation to promote the action and its results

The beneficiaries must promote the action and its results, by providing targeted information to multiple audiences (including the media and the public) in a strategic and effective manner.

Before engaging in a communication activity expected to have a major media impact, the beneficiaries must inform INEA.

Information on EU funding — Obligation and right to use the EU emblem

Unless INEA requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, any communication activity related to the action (including in electronic form, via social media, etc.) and any infrastructure, equipment and major results funded by the grant must:

(a) Display the EU emblem and

(b) Include the following text:

For communication activities: “This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 723265”.

For infrastructure, equipment and major results: “This [infrastructure][equipment][insert type of result] is part of a project that has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 723265”.

When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence.

For the purposes of their obligations under this Article, the beneficiaries may use the EU emblem without first obtaining approval from INEA.

This does not, however, give them the right to exclusive use.

Moreover, they may not appropriate the EU emblem or any similar trademark or logo, either by registration or by any other means.

Consequences of non-compliance

If a beneficiary breaches any of its obligations under this agreement, the grant may be reduced.

12.1.2 Dissemination of results — Open access — Visibility of EU funding

Regarding article 29, these are the rules to follow:

Obligation to disseminate results

Unless it goes against their legitimate interests, each beneficiary must — as soon as possible — ‘disseminate’ its results by disclosing them to the public by appropriate means (other than those resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including in scientific publications (in any medium).

A beneficiary that intends to disseminate its results must give advance notice to the other beneficiaries of — unless agreed otherwise — at least 45 days, together with sufficient information on the results it will disseminate.

Any other beneficiary may object within — unless agreed otherwise — 30 days of receiving notification, if it can show that its legitimate interests in relation to the results or background would be significantly harmed. In such cases, the dissemination may not take place unless appropriate steps are taken to safeguard these legitimate interests.

If a beneficiary intends not to protect its results, it may [...] need to formally notify the *Innovation and Networks Executive Agency (INEA)* before dissemination takes place.

Open access to scientific publications

Each beneficiary must ensure open access (free of charge online access for any user) to all peer reviewed scientific publications relating to its results.

The bibliographic metadata must be in a standard format and must include all of the following:

- The terms “European Union (EU)” and “Horizon 2020”;
- The name of the action, acronym and grant number;
- The publication date, and length of embargo period if applicable, and
- A persistent identifier.

Information on EU funding — Obligation and right to use the EU emblem

Unless INEA requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, any dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic) must:

(a) Display the EU emblem and

(b) Include the following text:

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 723265”.

When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence.

For the purposes of their obligations under this agreement, the beneficiaries may use the EU emblem without first obtaining approval from INEA.

This does not however give them the right to exclusive use.

Moreover, they may not appropriate the EU emblem or any similar trademark or logo, either by registration or by any other means.

Disclaimer excluding INEA responsibility

Any dissemination of results must indicate that it reflects only the author’s view and that INEA is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Consequences of non-compliance

If a beneficiary breaches any of its obligations under this agreement, the grant may be reduced.

12.1.3 Open access to scientific publications

Each beneficiary must ensure open access (free of charge online access for any user) to all peer reviewed scientific publications relating to its results.

The bibliographic metadata must be in a standard format and must include all of the following:

- The terms “European Union (EU)” and “Horizon 2020”;
- The name of the action, acronym and grant number;
- The publication date, and length of embargo period if applicable, and
- A persistent identifier.

An initial discussion regarding Open Access Repositories has been included in Annex 13.4 Open access repository.

13. ANNEX I - Other Social media

13.1 Facebook

Description

Facebook is a social networking service launched in February 2004, owned and operated by Facebook, Inc. Facebook has more than 2 billion monthly active users as of June 2017. As of April 2016, Facebook was the most popular social networking site in the world, based on the number of active user accounts. Users must register before using the site, after which they may create a personal profile, add other users as friends, and exchange messages, including automatic notifications when they update their profile. Additionally, users may join common-interest user groups, organized by workplace, school or college, or other characteristics.

Users can create profiles with photos, lists of personal interests, contact information, and other personal information. Users can communicate with friends and other users through private or public messages and a chat feature. They can also create and join interest groups and "like pages", some of which are maintained by organizations as a means of advertising. A 2012 Pew Internet and American Life study identified that between 20–30% of Facebook users are "power users" who frequently link, poke, post and tag themselves and others.

The like button is a social networking feature, allowing users to express their appreciation of content such as status updates, comments, photos, and advertisements.

Use

Given its popularity as social network, this tool could have an important role in the communication and dissemination activities. However, currently, the general profile of the user as well as its lack of focus on professional activities does **not recommend** this network for scientific or technical dissemination.

13.2 Wikipedia

Description

Wikipedia is a collaboratively edited, multilingual, free Internet encyclopedia supported by the non-profit Wikimedia Foundation. Its 24 million articles, over 4.1 million in the English Wikipedia, are written collaboratively by volunteers around the world. Almost all of its articles can be edited by anyone with access to the site. [...] It has become the largest and most popular general reference work on the Internet, ranking sixth globally among all websites on Alexa and having an estimated 365 million readers worldwide. (8)

Use

Although it is not a social network, Wikipedia is seen by many a key entrance point for the understanding of scientific and technical concepts. In this way, it could be interesting to include a page to explain the project, the goals, achievements and updates, with emphasis in the following factors:

- Technical concepts related to the issues of the project: inductive charging, electric vehicles, batteries, etc
- Other internet tools related to the project (Twitter, LinkedIn, Web site, etc.)

Given the nature and rules of Wikipedia, especially concerning the revision and approval procedures, it is important to avoid that the entry in Wikipedia may have seen as just a

promotion page, so both contents and language use should be carefully used. In addition, Wikipedia is a tertiary information source, which is fed by secondary information sources (independent from the primary information source, which are the originators of the information). This means that before establishing a Wikipedia entry, several secondary information sources should inform about Clusters 2.0.

13.3 Slideshare

Description

SlideShare is a Web 2.0 based slide hosting service. Users can upload files privately or publicly in the following file formats: PowerPoint, PDF, Keynote or OpenDocument presentations. Slide decks can then be viewed on the site itself, on hand held devices or embedded on other sites. Launched on October 4, 2006, the website is considered to be similar to YouTube, but for slideshows. The website was originally meant to be used for businesses to share slides among employees more easily, but it has since expanded to also become a host of a large number of slides that are uploaded merely to entertain. Although the website is primarily a slide hosting service, it also supports documents, PDFs, videos and webinars. SlideShare also provides users the ability to rate, comment on, and share the uploaded content...

SlideShare was voted among the World's Top 10 tools for education & e-learning in 2010.

On May 2012, SlideShare announced that it was to be acquired by LinkedIn.

Use

Although it was originally not a social network, Slideshare is seen by many a key entrance point for the understanding of scientific and technical concepts. In this way, it could be interesting to include a page to explain the project, the goals, achievements and updates, with emphasis in the following factors:

In this case, it is foreseen that presentations material related to the project findings should be made available. Using the Slideshare functionalities, a channel with its followers could become a platform for disseminating the project by sharing the public presentations to a wider audience, as well as an additional starting point for the audience, by using the right terms for the search.

13.4 Open access repository

Description

According Wikipedia an open access repository is a digital platform that holds research output and provide free, immediate and permanent access to research results to anyone to use, download and distribute. To facilitate open access such repositories must be interoperable according to the Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH). Search engines harvest the content of open access repositories, constructing a database of worldwide, free of charge available research.

Use

As opposed to simple institutional repository or disciplinary repository open access repositories provides free access to research to users outside the institutional community are one of the recommended ways to achieve the open access vision described in the Budapest Open Access Initiative definition of open access. This is sometimes referred to as "green" route to open access.

Following the H2020 rules regarding the publication of Dissemination information, including

 Clusters 2.0

documents, articles and datasets (if any is available), Clusters 2.0 will publish its information in a permanent Open Access repository. At the current moment the initial candidates include: ZENODO (a joint initiative of OpenAIRE and the CERN), Digital Commons, OALibrary (Open Access Library) or Open-Science-Repository. Among other considerations, being ready to be indexed by Google Scholar will be an important factor in the election.